

Assessment of Risk Factors and Outcomes in Preterm Infants with Bronchopulmonary Dysplasia: A Case-Control Study

Ankitkumar N. Patel¹, Mayur C. Gwalani², Chandra Prakash Soni³, Kishankumar J Nakum⁴, Anita Patel⁵

¹Senior Resident, Department of Paediatrics, Smt. N.H.L. Municipal Medical College, Ahmedabad, Gujarat, India

²Consultant Paediatrician, Nakshatra Multispeciality Hospital, Morbi, Gujarat, India

³Senior Resident, Department of Paediatrics, National Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India

⁴Consultant Paediatrician, Mothercare Multispeciality Hospital, Babra, Amreli, Gujarat, India

⁵Assistant Professor, Department of Anaesthesiology, Ananya College of Medicine and Research, Kalol, Gandhinagar, Gujarat, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Kishankumar J Nakum

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Abstract:

Background: Bronchopulmonary dysplasia (BPD) is a chronic lung disease affecting preterm neonates, particularly those born before 32 weeks gestation. Despite advances in care, BPD continues to cause significant morbidity and mortality. It is strongly associated with prolonged oxygen therapy, mechanical ventilation, sepsis, ventilator-associated pneumonia and NEC. Identifying and understanding these risk factors is essential for improving outcomes for preterm infants in neonatal intensive care units.

Aims and Objectives: The aim of this study was to assess the risk factors and outcomes associated with BPD in preterm infants.

Materials and Methods: This case-control study was conducted in the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) of a tertiary care hospital in Gujarat over six months. Cases were pre term infants diagnosed with BPD, while controls were preterm infants without BPD. Key risk factors such as gestational age, birth weight, sepsis, and respiratory interventions were assessed. Data were collected retrospectively from medical records, and statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 20, with p-values < 0.05 considered significant.

Results: The study included 100 infants with BPD and 100 controls. The BPD group had significantly lower gestational age (29.3 ± 1.9 weeks vs. 31.2 ± 2.1 weeks, $p < 0.001$) and birth weight (1.23 ± 0.76 kg vs. 1.56 ± 0.86 kg, $p < 0.001$). Sepsis, both early-onset (32% vs. 12%, $p = 0.001$) and late-onset (42% vs. 11%, $p < 0.001$), was significantly more common in the BPD group. Complications like patent ductus arteriosus (38% vs. 12%, $p < 0.001$), and pulmonary hypertension (9% vs. 1%, $p = 0.01$) were also higher in the BPD group. Mechanical ventilation use was also higher in Infants with BPD (89% vs. 22%, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: Preterm infants with lower gestational age, lower birth weight, and higher incidence of sepsis, VAP, NEC, and prolonged oxygen therapy are at increased risk of developing BPD. Early identification and management of these risk factors may reduce BPD incidence and improve long-term outcomes for preterm infants in India.

Keywords: Bronchopulmonary Dysplasia, Mechanical Ventilation, Preterm Infants, Sepsis, Risk Factors, Ventilator-Associated Pneumonia.

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Introduction

Bronchopulmonary dysplasia (BPD) is a chronic lung disease affecting approximately 50% of preterm neonates born before 28 weeks of gestation and 30% of those born before 32 weeks. [1,2] Mortality is higher among infants with BPD. [3] Traditionally, BPD was associated with severe lung injury due to assisted ventilation and oxygen therapy in premature, noncompliant lungs. The introduction of surfactant therapy has modified its

pathophysiology; however, BPD remains prevalent in very low-birth-weight (VLBW) infants (<1500 g), including those requiring minimal to moderate respiratory support in the early postnatal period. [4–6]

Survivors of BPD often face significant pulmonary and non-pulmonary morbidities, such as cerebral palsy and growth, developmental, and academic challenges. Optimizing care delivery systems,

including regional referral for at-risk infants, is critical. Identifying risk factors could allow for targeted therapies to reduce BPD incidence or severity and improve long-term outcomes. [7]

The etiology of BPD is multifactorial, involving genetic predispositions and prenatal and postnatal environmental influences. Known risk factors include lower birth weight, younger gestational age, male sex, fetal growth restriction, and prolonged ventilator-induced injury. [8,9] Medical care practices, as part of the postnatal environment, are also influential. Studies have shown variations in BPD incidence across regional perinatal centers, highlighting concerns about VLBW infant mortality when care is provided outside regional and tertiary centers. The impact of the deregionalization of neonatal care on BPD risk remains unclear. [7]

Inflammation plays a critical role in BPD development. Prenatal inflammation can disrupt fetal lung development, increasing the risk of BPD in preterm infants. Prolonged respiratory support and sepsis further predispose infants to BPD by inducing proinflammatory and profibrotic responses in the lungs. In animal models, hyperoxia-induced BPD is worsened by episodes of hypoxia, leading to oxidative stress, inflammation, and fibrosis of the alveolar septum, impairing lung development. [10]

In India, BPD is increasingly recognized as a significant complication among preterm infants. Despite improvements in neonatal care, data on BPD-specific risk factors and outcomes in Indian settings remain limited. Understanding these factors is crucial for developing prevention and management strategies tailored to the needs of preterm infants in India. This study aims to investigate the risk factors and outcomes associated with BPD in preterm infants admitted to a tertiary care NICU in India. By identifying modifiable risk factors, this research seeks to inform targeted interventions to reduce the incidence and severity of BPD in this vulnerable population.

Material and Methods

Study Design: This is a case-control study aimed at assessing the risk factors and outcomes associated with BPD in preterm infants.

Study Setting and Duration: The study was conducted in the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) of a tertiary care hospital in Gujarat over a period of 6 months.

Study Population: The study population comprised preterm infants admitted to the NICU during the study period.

- **Cases:** Infants diagnosed with bronchopulmonary dysplasia (BPD) were included as cases. BPD was defined using the NICHD criteria, which include the need for

supplemental oxygen for at least 28 days postnatally, along with radiographic evidence consistent with BPD.

- **Controls:** The control group consisted of preterm infants admitted to the NICU who did not develop BPD.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Preterm infants born at less than 32 weeks of gestation.
- Infants with a birth weight of less than 1500 grams.
- Admission to the NICU within 24 hours of birth.
- Availability of complete medical records.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Infants with congenital anomalies or chromosomal abnormalities.
- Infants who died within the first 7 days of life.
- Infants with incomplete medical records.

Ethical Considerations: The study protocol was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee of the tertiary care hospital. Patient confidentiality and data privacy were strictly maintained throughout the study.

A diagnosis of BPD was defined by a requirement of oxygen supplementation at 36 weeks postmenstrual age (PMA).¹⁰

Data Collection: Data were retrospectively extracted from medical records using a structured data collection form. The following variables were recorded:

- **Maternal and neonatal demographics:** Maternal age, antenatal corticosteroid administration, mode of delivery, premature rupture of membranes (PROM), gestational age, birth weight, and sex.
- **Risk factors for BPD:** Duration of mechanical ventilation, use of surfactant, duration of oxygen therapy, incidence of neonatal sepsis, and presence of patent ductus arteriosus (PDA), early onset sepsis (EOS), late-onset sepsis (LOS), central line-associated bloodstream infections (CLABSI), ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP), necrotizing enterocolitis (NEC)
- **Outcomes:** Length of hospital stay, respiratory support, surfactant treatment, incidence of retinopathy of prematurity (ROP), neurodevelopmental outcomes, and mortality.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS, version 20. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize baseline characteristics of the study population. Continuous variables were presented as

mean \pm standard deviation, and categorical variables as frequencies and percentages. The association between each risk factor and the development of BPD was assessed using chi-square tests for categorical variables and t-tests for continuous

variables. The p value less than 0.05 was considered as significant.

Results

Table 1: Comparison of perinatal and neonatal characteristics between preterm infants with and without BPD

Characteristics	BPD (n=100)	No BPD (n=100)	p value
Perinatal history			
Maternal age (years)	35.3 \pm 9.4	34.7 \pm 7.8	0.67
Chorioamnionitis	12 (12%)	10 (10%)	0.82
Uterine infection	3 (3%)	2 (2%)	1.00
Diabetes Mellitus	8 (8%)	11 (11%)	0.63
Hypertension	20 (20%)	24 (24%)	0.61
Bleeding/abruption/previa	24 (24%)	20 (20%)	0.61
Mal-presentation	34 (34%)	26 (26%)	0.28
Premature ROM	43 (43%)	32 (32%)	0.14
Prolonged ROM	20 (20%)	18 (18%)	0.85
No antenatal steroids	32 (32%)	24 (24%)	0.27
Caesarean delivery	75 (75%)	80 (80%)	0.49
Neonatal characteristics			
Gestational age (week)	29.3 \pm 1.9	31.2 \pm 2.1	< 0.001
Birth weight	1.23 \pm 0.76	1.56 \pm 0.86	< 0.001
Multiple birth	29 (29%)	31 (31%)	0.87
Male sex	56 (56%)	42 (42%)	0.07
IUGR	10 (10%)	9 (9%)	1.00
MSAF	10 (10%)	6 (6%)	0.43
Sepsis	75 (75%)	23 (23%)	< 0.001
EOS	32 (32%)	12 (12%)	0.001
LOS	42 (42%)	11 (11%)	< 0.001
CLABSI	4 (4%)	3 (3%)	1.00
VAP	18 (18%)	1 (1%)	< 0.001
Meningitis	10 (10%)	3 (3%)	0.08
NEC	18 (18%)	7 (7%)	0.03
PDA	38 (38%)	12 (12%)	< 0.001
PH	9 (9%)	1 (1%)	0.01
IVH	28 (28%)	1 (1%)	< 0.001
PVL	10 (10%)	3 (3%)	0.08
ROP	29 (29%)	12 (12%)	0.004
Total days in hospital	65.3 \pm 10.2	43.2 \pm 8.1	< 0.001

In this study, the mean maternal age was 35.3 \pm 9.4 years for the BPD group and 34.7 \pm 7.8 years for the non-BPD group, with no significant difference ($p = 0.67$). Conditions like chorioamnionitis, uterine infections, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, bleeding disorders, mal-presentation, PROM, and caesarean delivery were similar between both groups.

Neonatal characteristics revealed significant differences. The BPD group had a lower mean gestational age (29.3 \pm 1.9 weeks) compared to the non-BPD group (31.2 \pm 2.1 weeks, $p < 0.001$). The mean birth weight was also lower in the BPD group (1.23 \pm 0.76 kg vs. 1.56 \pm 0.86 kg, $p < 0.001$).

The incidence of sepsis (75% vs 23%, $p < 0.001$), including EOS (32% vs. 12%, $p = 0.001$) and LOS (42% vs. 11%, $p < 0.001$), was significantly higher in infants with BPD. Ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) was significantly higher in the BPD group (18%) compared to the non-BPD group (1%, $p < 0.001$). Other complications such as NEC (18% vs. 7%, $p = 0.03$), PDA (38% vs. 12%, $p < 0.001$), pulmonary hypertension (PH) (9% vs. 1%, $p = 0.01$), intraventricular hemorrhage (IVH) (28% vs. 1%, $p < 0.001$), and retinopathy of prematurity (ROP) (29% vs. 12%, $p = 0.004$) were significantly higher in the BPD group. Infants with BPD also had significantly longer hospital stays (65.3 \pm 10.2 days vs. 43.2 \pm 8.1 days, $p < 0.001$).

Table 2: Comparison of respiratory support between preterm infants with and without BPD

Intervention	BPD (n=100)	No BPD (n=100)	p value
Postnatal steroid	65 (65%)	42 (42%)	0.001
Use of Surfactant	88 (88%)	47 (47%)	< 0.001
CPAP	100 (100%)	96 (96%)	0.12
NIPPV	99 (99%)	42 (42%)	< 0.001
CMV	89 (89%)	22 (22%)	< 0.001
HFOV	12 (12%)	4 (4%)	0.06

The use of postnatal steroids (65% vs. 42%, $p = 0.001$), use of surfactant (88% vs. 47%, $p < 0.001$), NIPPV (99% vs. 42%, $p < 0.001$), and CMV (89% vs. 22%, $p < 0.001$) were significantly higher in the BPD group ($p < 0.001$) compared to Non BPD groups.

Discussion

Studies have identified three respiratory patterns in preterm infants: mild disease with gradual recovery, early persistent deterioration needing prolonged support, and initial recovery followed by decompensation. [11,12] Advances in care, such as synchronized ventilation, lung volume standardization, non-invasive ventilation, early surfactant, and antenatal steroids, have shaped the current clinical population. [12] The present study aimed to assess the risk factors and outcomes associated with BPD in preterm infants through a case-control design.

Perinatal History

In the present study, maternal age, chorioamnionitis, uterine infection, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and other maternal complications did not show significant differences between BPD and non-BPD groups. However, in Lapcharoensap et al. [7] and Xu et al. [10], these factors were significantly associated with BPD, particularly uterine infection ($p < 0.001$), highlighting the potential impact of intrauterine infections in lower birth weight infants, a difference potentially attributable to population characteristics. Previous meta-analyses demonstrated that while antenatal corticosteroids may decrease the incidence of respiratory distress syndrome, it does not reduce the incidence of BPD. [9,13]

Neonatal Characteristics

Gestational age (GA) is the strongest predictor of BPD, especially in extremely premature infants, whose lung development is interrupted. These infants are prone to developing BPD regardless of postnatal management. [14] In this study, GA and birth weight were significantly lower in the BPD group (29.3 ± 1.9 weeks and 1.23 ± 0.76 kg), consistent with findings from Xu et al. [10] and Alonso et al.¹⁴, where lower GA and birth weights were linked to BPD ($p < 0.001$). Male gender, trending towards significance here ($p = 0.07$), is recognized as a risk factor for BPD, especially in larger cohorts like Lapcharoensap et al. [7] ($p < 0.001$). The NICHD network reported a 73% BPD

incidence at 23 weeks GA, with 56% having severe BPD, compared to 23% incidence at 28 weeks, with 8% having severe cases. Additionally, male infants are at a higher risk of developing BPD than females. The risk of BPD ranges from <10% to >40% among the Neonatal Research Network centers in infants <1250 grams birth weight. [15]

Infections

In the present study, Sepsis, both EOS and LOS, were strong predictors of BPD, occurring in 42% of BPD cases versus 11% in non-BPD cases ($p < 0.001$). This aligns with studies by Xu et al.¹⁰ and Alonso et al. [14], which also found EOS and LOS to be strongly associated with BPD ($p < 0.001$). A recent study of VLBW infants (24–28 weeks) identified LOS as a significant risk factor for BPD at 25–28 weeks, with effective postpartum resuscitation influencing BPD severity at 24 weeks. While intrauterine infection had minimal impact, neonatal sepsis significantly increased BPD risk. [16] Cokyaman et al. [17] further emphasized LOS (OR 2.7; 95% CI 1.6–4.5; $p < 0.01$) as a major contributor, with multiple episodes linked to severe cases. NEC and LOS may increase BPD risk through inflammation that impairs lung development and prolongs mechanical ventilation, worsening lung injury. [18,19] The systemic inflammatory response in sepsis, involving pro-inflammatory cytokines, PMN migration, and changes in vascular permeability, causes acute alveolar damage and may contribute to long-term arrest of alveolarization seen in BPD. [20]

In the present study, VAP and NEC were also more frequent in the BPD group ($p = 0.03$ and $p < 0.001$, respectively), reinforcing the role of nosocomial infections in BPD pathogenesis. VAP significantly contributes to morbidity by prolonging ventilation and increasing the risk of BPD. Wang et al. [21] reported that 25.4% of neonatal VAP cases were polymicrobial, often seen in neonates with extended intubation and chronic conditions like BPD.

Cardiovascular and Respiratory Risk Factors

In the present study, PDA and PH were significantly more common in the BPD group, with PDA present in 38% of cases ($p < 0.001$). These findings are consistent across the cohorts by Lapcharoensap et al.⁷ and Alonso et al. [14], suggesting that cardiovascular complications play a critical role in the

progression of BPD. The presence of a PDA has been associated with the need for prolonged mechanical ventilation, increased mortality and a higher risk of BPD. [20] Meta-analyses and systematic reviews indicate that PDA closure, whether pharmacologic or surgical, does not significantly reduce BPD risk. While PDA presence might be a marker for BPD risk, the variability in study designs complicates the assessment of PDA closure strategies. [20]

Respiratory Support

In the present study, infants with BPD in this study had significantly higher usage of postnatal steroids (65% vs. 42%, $p = 0.001$) and surfactant (88% vs. 47%, $p < 0.001$). These trends mirror those observed in Xu et al. [10], where the use of postnatal steroids and surfactants was associated with increased risk of BPD. Postnatal surfactant was a significant risk factor for BPD, with severe RDS being a common secondary trigger. [17] Two Cochrane reviews examined post-natal systemic steroid treatments. Early corticosteroid treatment (before day 8) showed a higher risk of cerebral palsy (RR 1.45, 95% CI 1.06-1.98), particularly with motor function impairment. Late corticosteroid treatment (after 7 days) demonstrated benefits, reducing the risks of BPD and death or CLD at both 28 days and 36 weeks PMA (RR 0.72, 95% CI 0.63-0.82), though with some risk of abnormal neurological exams but no increase in cerebral palsy. [22,23] Meta-regression analysis by Doyle et al. [24] showed that while corticosteroids increased the risk of cerebral palsy, they reduced the risk of death or CP in infants with a high BPD risk (>65%).

In the present study, the need for mechanical ventilation (89% in BPD vs. 22% in non-BPD, $p < 0.001$) was significantly higher, further supporting the literature on prolonged respiratory support as a contributor to BPD development. Higher airway pressure can help reduce oxygen requirements in preterm infants needing respiratory support. However, peak inspiratory pressure is a strong predictor of BPD development in these infants. Increased airway pressure is more likely to cause pulmonary barotrauma, which can trigger an inflammatory response, ultimately leading to BPD.¹⁰ Avoiding mechanical ventilation can reduce the risk of lung injury and BPD, potentially explaining some differences in BPD rates across centers. The use of nasal CPAP has shown success in some infants by reducing the need for mechanical ventilation, potentially lowering BPD risk. In term and near-term infants, resuscitation with room air is associated with lower mortality compared to 100% oxygen (RR=0.71). [25] Supplemental oxygen may be harmful, potentially causing oxidative injury to lung and brain tissues, though it is essential for preventing hypoxemia. The BOOST-I trial showed that higher oxygen saturations (95–98%) led to prolonged oxygen therapy without

affecting growth or development at 12 months. [26] The SUPPORT trial indicated no significant difference in BPD rates between lower (85–89%) and higher (91–95%) oxygen saturation targets, suggesting that the severity of illness, rather than oxygen toxicity, is more closely linked to BPD risk. The lower saturation group also had increased mortality. [27]

Conclusion

This study highlights gestational age, birth weight, sepsis, and mechanical ventilation as key risk factors for BPD in preterm infants. Male gender, PDA, PH, and infections such as NEC and VAP further contribute to the risk of BPD. While maternal factors were not strongly associated with BPD in this study. Postnatal steroids and surfactants were more frequently used in BPD cases, reflecting the complexity of managing respiratory distress in this vulnerable population. Reducing mechanical ventilation and optimizing infection control may help mitigate BPD risk in preterm infants.

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